

CONTINUITY, TRANSFORMATION AND TRANSFER OF SPATIAL SACREDNESS: THE EXAMPLE OF MENDERES BASIN

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ABSTRACT

The Menderes Basin has historically been a sacred geography where different religions and beliefs have intertwined, where the sacred manifests in multilayered forms, and where cult-centered structures have come to the forefront. The sacred sites in this region—where religious practices and rituals have been intensely present throughout history—hold particular significance for understanding the sustainability of religious collective memory and the expression of religious identity. The sacred sites identified in the Menderes Basin were originally designated as episcopal centers following the adoption of Christianity, long before the settlement of Turks in the region. With the arrival of Turks and the adoption of Islam in Anatolia, Islamic structures such as shrines and tombs began to emerge, particularly in and around these earlier religious centers, more densely than in other areas. This process involves not only a physical transformation but also the transmission and reconstruction of sacredness. The Menderes Basin, through these religious spaces that have maintained their sanctity from past to present, stands as a unique archetype of syncretic transformation, transmission, and continuity—where rituals and mystical narratives that symbolically express and esoterically support the religious and cultural codes of communities are performed. This study addresses sacred site transformations under distinct categories such as peaceful transmission, power-driven transmission, reoccupation of abandoned sacred spaces, and transmission through narratives, objects, and dreams. The theoretical framework draws upon Rudolf Otto's emphasis on the transcendent nature of the sacred, Durkheim's interpretation of the social construction of sacredness, Eliade's sacred-profane dichotomy, and the collective and cultural memory theories of Halbwachs, Assmann, and Nora. Accordingly, the study aims to demonstrate that spatial sacredness is sustained not only as a theological phenomenon but also as a sociological, phenomenological, and memory-based reality. The syncretic and eclectic transformations of sacred sites in the Menderes Basin offer significant insights into understanding religious and cultural continuity in Anatolia and aim to contribute both theoretically and methodologically to future research.

Keywords: Sacred Place, Ritual, Sacred Personality, Mystical Narrative, Syncretism.

MEKÂNSAL KUTSİYETİN SÜREKLİLİĞİ, DÖNÜŞÜMÜ VE AKTARIMI: MENDERES HAVZASI ÖRNEĞİ

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ÖZET

Menderes Havzası, tarih boyunca farklı inanç ve dinlerin iç içe geçtiği; kutsalın çok katmanlı biçimlerde tezahür ettiği bir inanç coğrafyasıdır. Tarihsel süreçte inançların ve dinî ritüellerin yoğun olarak kendini gösterdiği bu bölgede yer alan kutsal mekânlar, dinî kolektif hafızanın sürdürülebilirliğini görmek ve dinsel kimliğin dışavurumunu anlamak açısından özel bir öneme sahiptir. Menderes Havzası'nda tespit edilen kutsal mekânlar,

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Türklerin bölgeye yerleşiminden önce Hristiyanlığın kabulüyle birlikte piskoposluk merkezi olarak addedilen dini merkezlerdir. Bu dini merkezler daha öncesinde de kült ve tapınakların bulunduğu kutsal alanlardır. İslamiyet'in kabul edilmesi ve Türklerin Anadolu'ya gelişiyle birlikte bu merkezlerde ve onların yakın çevresinde diğer bölgelere kıyasla daha yoğun bir şekilde yatır ve türbe gibi İslami yapılar ortaya çıkmıştır. Bu süreç, yalnızca fiziksel dönüşümü değil; aynı zamanda kutsallığın aktarımı ve yeniden inşasını da içermektedir. Bu bağlamda Menderes Havzası, geçmişten günümüze kutsallığını koruyarak varlığını sürdüren kutsal mekânlar aracılığıyla, toplumların dini ve kültürel kodlarını ezoterik anlatılarla destekleyip sembolik ifadelerle aktaran ritüellerin ve mistik anlatıların sergilendiği senkretik değişim, dönüşüm ve aktarımın özgün bir arketipi olarak karşımıza çıkmaktadır. Çalışmada kutsal mekân dönüşümleri; barışçıl aktarım, güce dayalı aktarım ve terk edilen mekâna yeniden yerleşim, anlatı, nesne ve rüya yoluyla aktarım gibi özgün başlıklarla ele alınmıştır. Kuramsal zeminde Rudolf Otto'nun kutsalın aşkın doğasını vurgulayan yaklaşımı, Durkheim'in kutsallığın toplumsal inşasına yönelik yorumu, Eliade'nin kutsal-profân ayrımı ve Halbwachs, Assmann ile Nora'nın kolektif ve kültürel hafıza kuramları temel alınmıştır. Bu çalışma, mekânsal kutsiyetin yalnızca teolojik değil aynı zamanda sosyolojik, fenomenolojik ve kolektif hafızaya dayalı bir gerçeklik olarak sürdürüldüğünü göstermeyi amaçlamaktadır. Menderes Havzası'ndaki kutsal mekânların senkretik ve eklektik dönüşümleri üzerinden yürütülen incelemeler, Anadolu'daki dini-kültürel sürekliliği anlamaya yönelik önemli veriler sunmakta; gelecek çalışmalara hem teorik hem de yöntemsel katkı sağlamayı hedeflemektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kutsal Mekân, Ritüeller, Kutsal Şahsiyet, Mistik Anlatı, Senkretizm.

Introduction

The Menderes Basin stands out as a unique geography of belief where the sacred is continually reproduced over time. Within this basin, the regions of particular significance for this study are sacred sites where religious traditions and beliefs have been intensely present throughout history, offering a unique lens through which to observe the sustainability of religious collective memory and the expression of religious identity (Cangul, 2024: 11). Most of the sacred sites identified in the Menderes Basin were designated as episcopal centers with the spread of Christianity prior to the settlement of the Turks in the region and functioned as important regional cult and worship centers. These spaces were recontextualized with the advent of Christianity, ensuring continuity by harmonizing their sacredness with the new belief system. The religious significance carried from antiquity was reinforced during the early Christian period, and churches, chapels, and ayazmas built across the basin stand today as tangible architectural manifestations of this continuity.

Following the spread of Islam in Anatolia and the settlement of Turks in the region, similar religious structures emerged around these sacred centers, often echoing their earlier functions. Structures such as shrines (yatır), tombs (türbe), and other Islamic religious sites became increasingly prominent, frequently built atop or adjacent to pre-existing sacred places. This indicates not only a transformation in the physical landscape but also a spatial and functional transmission of sacredness, reconstructed through a process of syncretism. These sites thus became spatial expressions of interreligious transitions, bearing witness to syncretic transformations in an eclectic context. In this sense, the Menderes Basin serves not only as a historical heritage zone but also as a living laboratory where sacred spaces inherited from the past are continuously sanctified through collective memory and religious imagination. Through symbolic practices such as prayer, vows, offerings, cloth-tying, and candle-lighting, communities expressed their beliefs and sustained their collective memory. Mystical narratives, dreams, and hagiographies reinforced this transmission of sacredness, fostering a spiritual sense of belonging to place. Consequently, the sacred sites in the Menderes Basin emerge as archetypes of syncretic transformation, change, and transmission, providing key insights into the formation of memoryscapes and the construction of cultural identity. In this respect, the basin plays a vital role in understanding the multi-layered religious geography of Anatolia.

This study seeks to examine how belief systems that influenced the lifestyle of early Turkic communities shaped Christian and Muslim sacred spaces, perceptions of visitation, and mystical narratives surrounding holy figures. Drawing upon shared features and parallels in visitation practices—especially those pointing to ancient Turkic beliefs—examples from Ancient Greek, Christian, and Muslim sacred traditions are presented. The recurrence of motifs and narrative structures in mystical stories of Christian saints and Muslim saints (erenler) reveals that despite temporal and spatial shifts, the narrative essence and religious fabric remained largely intact. The religious codes surrounding the sacred were examined through mystical narratives and analyzed through the lens of religious syncretism.

The concept of sacred space was addressed not only from theological perspectives but also from sociological and phenomenological standpoints. The theoretical framework included Rudolf Otto's ontological approach to the sacred as a transcendent and numinous reality, Émile Durkheim's sociological interpretation of sacredness as a product of social consensus and ritual practices, and Mircea Eliade's phenomenological view that locates sacred space as a cosmic center through the sacred-profane dichotomy. Additionally, the theories of collective and cultural memory as represented by Maurice Halbwachs, Jan Assmann, and Pierre Nora provided an analytical foundation. Based on this framework, the sustainability of spatial sacredness in the Menderes Basin is proposed to be nourished both by transcendent belief and by collective memory.

The transformations identified in this study are categorized under seven headings. Three of these "Peaceful Transfer," "Transfer by Power," and "Reoccupation of Abandoned Sacred Spaces" are based on Hasluck's classification (2012: 54). The remaining four "Transfer by Constructing a New Sacred Site Adjacent to the Existing One," "Transfer through Sacred Objects," "Transfer through Narrative," and "Transfer through Dream" are original typologies developed in this study based on fieldwork in the Menderes Basin. Each form of transmission is illustrated with localized examples, analyzing their roles within religious continuity, cultural transmission, and collective memory.

When examining sacred spaces, ritual practices, holy figures, and mystical narratives in Turkey as separate categories, the cultural context often appears lacking. This study explicitly foregrounds this cultural context and the process of enculturation, aiming to uncover the long-standing relationship between belief systems and cultural forms from prehistoric times to the present. In doing so, this research aspires to serve as a model for future studies on sacred sites, rituals, sacred figures, and mystical narratives, encouraging the application of religious syncretism as a methodological tool. By interpreting belief systems through this syncretic lens within their broader social context, this work contributes a distinctive depth to the literature. Ultimately, such explorations into the foundations of religious perceptions in Anatolia allow for a deeper understanding of folk beliefs shaped by religion and the syncretic dimensions of religious culture itself.

1) Interpreting Sacred Space and the Continuity of Spatial Sacredness

The concept of sacred space lies at the heart of numerous philosophical, sociological, and phenomenological debates. These discussions on the nature of the sacred are directly linked to both the individual's experience of the sacred and society's symbolic constructions. A key distinction emerging from these debates is the directional difference between the notions of "space emerging from the sacred" and "the sacred emerging from space" (Tatar, 2017: 13–15). From an ontological perspective, Rudolf Otto places the sacred at the center as a *numinous*

experience. According to Otto, the sacred is not part of the phenomenal world; rather, it is a reality in and of itself. In this approach, sacred space is understood as a site where the sacred manifests itself spontaneously (*hierophany*) (Otto, 1958: 13). Thus, space holds a secondary position, deriving its sanctity from a transcendent force. The meaning of space becomes possible through the sacred's permeation from its ontological realm. Here, the sacred is pre-existent, and space functions merely as its locus of manifestation.

In contrast to this view, the sociological approach represented by Émile Durkheim sees the sacred as a product of society rather than a transcendent reality. For Durkheim, the sacred does not rest upon a supernatural or supra-individual truth, but rather upon society itself. Through rituals, symbols, and social practices, certain places are ascribed with sacredness (Durkheim, 2005: 158–166). Accordingly, sacred space is not the result of a transcendent power, but of a culturally produced and socially constructed system of meaning. In this context, sacredness is not a divine descent from the heavens but a socially rooted meaning.

Occupying a middle ground between these two approaches, Mircea Eliade follows a phenomenological line of thought while emphasizing that the sacred manifests as a structure within space. Eliade's distinction between the sacred and the profane reflects Durkheim's sociological perspective but also asserts the sacred as an ontological reality. For Eliade, every sacred space is a symbolic center of the cosmos. This center becomes an axis that organizes the chaos of the universe and has the power to render the profane sacred (Eliade, 2003: 15–40). Thus, Eliade develops a dual perspective that highlights both the transcendental and experiential dimensions of the sacred. In this framework, sacred space is not merely a place; it is a threshold where time halts and cosmic order is revealed.

Adding another dimension to these debates, Georg Simmel's essay *Bridge and Door* introduces a fresh philosophical insight. Simmel argues that humans are beings who simultaneously draw and transcend boundaries, and therefore all dualities—such as sacred-profane, inner-outer, self-other—entail both separation and union. His position resonates with Hegelian thought, which seeks to move beyond Kantian dichotomies: the human being defines the sacred by establishing distance, while simultaneously harboring a desire to approach it (Kaern, 1994: 407–412). This paradox renders sacred space not only a “set-apart” domain but also a “sought-after” one. The metaphors of bridge and door here symbolize the dual nature of sacred space as both separator and connector (Tatar, 2017: 10).

Beyond these perspectives, a fourth approach is also conceivable. This view posits that the entire universe is inherently sacred, and specific sacred spaces are microcosmic reflections of this universal sacredness. According to this understanding, sacred spaces represent microcosms of the entire cosmos, which is itself sacred. It emphasizes the absoluteness of the sacred in contrast to the finitude of human existence. In this light, sacred spaces become symbolic domains that remind humanity of its spatial and existential limitations in the face of the absolute. In the context of the Qur'anic verse “*Allah is the Light of the heavens and the earth*” (Nur 24:35), the universe is conceived as a transparent and transcendent field of reflection. However, this notion of transparency is, throughout human history, often distorted and obscured—especially through the concept of *bid'a* (innovation)—eventually giving way to more opaque and closed imaginations of space. Particularly in modern Islamic thought, as articulated by theorists like Sayyid Qutb and Mawdudi, the contemporary world is viewed as a new *Jahiliyyah* era; thus, sacred space transforms into a realm that is no longer luminous or accessible, but rather sealed off from the transcendent (Tatar, 2017: 10–20). In this understanding, sacred space also carries a complex architectural symbolism. Architectural

elements such as doors, thresholds, bridges, windows, and passages are not merely physical structures but metaphoric realms mediating between dualities like spirit-body, inner-outer, sacred-profane (Bakshi, 2011: 46). Hence, sacred space represents not only divine manifestation but also the metaphysical journey of the individual. Reminiscent of Plato's distinction between the world of forms and the physical world, sacred spaces become thresholds—spiritually desired yet physically always just beyond reach.

At this juncture, it becomes essential to delve into the linguistic and semantic foundations of sacred space. Heidegger's proposition that "*language is the house of Being*" implies that sacred space is constructed not only physically but also linguistically, historically, and narratively (Heidegger: 243). In this context, the sacred-profane distinction arises not so much from geographic differences in the outer world but from narrative realms shaped by human consciousness. Sacred space, while being a locus where the transcendent is symbolically manifested, also functions as a site of memory where people accumulate religious experiences and shape future imaginaries. Thus, sacred space is not merely an architectural ensemble but an "event space" where time, faith, cultural memory, and social history converge. The fact that the Arabic terms *makān* (space) and *kawn* (being) share the same etymological root further suggests that space can be understood as a realm of emergence and manifestation. Therefore, sacred space may be defined as a realm where divine power manifests and where this manifestation is recognized and validated by observers. Through *shi'ār*—a set of symbols and rituals—this manifestation is made visible and intelligible. As exemplified by the *Bayt Allah*, the simultaneous manifestation of the farthest transcendence in the closest proximity renders space both visible and inaccessible (Tatar, 2017: 17). Thus, sacred space transforms into a liminal zone characterized by the paradox of proximity and distance. In phenomenological analyses, this liminality can also be explained through the concepts of "lived" and "experienced" spaces. Burhanettin Tatar's analysis emphasizes that sacred space is both a living experience and a memory field storing the religious practices of the past (Tatar, 2017). In this regard, structures like churches, ayazmas, shrines (*yatır*), and tombs (*türbe*) are not only places of worship but also shared spaces that express communal memory and religious practices through aesthetic, architectural, and ritual forms. These structures should be considered syncretic spaces that result from the fusion of diverse cultural elements over time.

Syncretism here refers not merely to the amalgamation of different religious traditions but also to the reinterpretation of sacred space through multiple perspectives. Especially in the Anatolian context, the transformation of rural Christian chapels into *yatır* or *türbe* cults over time reveals the syncretic structure shaped by folk Islam, local beliefs, and traditional practices (Cangul, 2024: 76). In this process, while space is sanctified under the control of formal Islamic doctrine, it simultaneously becomes a living and evolving field of meaning through folk beliefs, hagiographies, dreams, votive rituals, and cloth-tying practices. In this respect, sacred spaces appear—within the framework of Jan Assmann's concept of cultural memory—as symbolic realms where the past is continuously reconstructed. According to Assmann, cultural memory goes beyond personal or everyday memory, referring to a world of meaning transmitted across generations through written sources, rituals, symbols, and architectural structures. Cultural memory not only enables remembrance of the past but also facilitates the reconstruction of present identity (Assmann, 1995: 126). The transformation of a former cult center into a *türbe* involves not just physical change but also shifts in symbolic and ritual practices. However, this transformation represents not rupture but continuity. The locus of the sacred does not change—only its language, symbolism, and expressions do. In this sense, space becomes a vehicle of cultural continuity.

Maurice Halbwachs' theory of collective memory also demonstrates that sacred spaces play a central role in the construction of communal identity and the reinforcement of a sense of belonging. He argues that individuals can remember the past only through the frameworks provided by the social groups they belong to. Accordingly, sacred spaces are not formed by individuals, but by communities, and their continuity depends on this shared memory (Halbwachs, 2018: 63–78). For instance, the construction of a church over a pagan temple and, later, the recognition of the same site as sacred through a *yatır* or *türbe* by the community shows that the place continues to be perceived not for its physical function but as a space imbued with sacred memory. Memory here functions not only as a recollection of the past but also as a process of reinterpreting the past within the present.

Pierre Nora's concept of "lieux de mémoire" (sites of memory) regards these spaces not merely as physical locations but as places where cultural, historical, and symbolic narratives are intertwined. According to Nora, as modern societies lose their direct connection with the past, memory becomes increasingly dependent on specific spaces, rituals, and symbols. Although these sites may have served different religious systems throughout various historical periods, what unites them is the continued enactment of the "sacred" through space (Nora, 2006: 17–36). In this context, the continuity of sacred spaces is not simply the repetition of religious memory; it also depends on the capacity of these places to be reinterpreted, transformed, and infused with multiple layers of meaning. Especially in ancient settlement regions such as the Menderes Basin, the transformation of rural Christian sanctuaries into Muslim shrines (*yatır*) over time reveals the syncretic evolution of the sacred across different historical epochs. These kinds of transformations demonstrate that sacred spaces are not solely reflections of the divine, but also places woven anew through collective memory, shaped by local narratives, and kept alive through ritual practices.

The multi-layered structure observed in the Menderes Basin shows that what sustains the continuity of sacred spaces is the shared meanings generated by the communities that re-sanctify these sites in every era through memory, narrative, and representation. Therefore, sacred space emerges as an existential domain experienced through temporal depth, shaped by narratives, oscillating between transcendence and immanence, and embodying the entwinement of diverse belief systems and cultural practices. Such a domain sustains its sanctity not only through the manifestation of the divine but also through the integration of folk beliefs, architectural representations, collective memory, and ritual practices.

2. The Reconstruction of the Sacred: Social Memory, Belief, and the Transformation of Space

Sacred spaces are not merely venues for religious worship; they are also locations imbued with the traces of the past, where social memory becomes spatialized and collective identity is continually reproduced. People benefit from the atmosphere of these spaces to construct meaning, achieve psychosocial harmony, assert power in the context of the state, or seek spiritual refuge in response to life's adversities (Cangul, 2024: 76). Structures such as temples, churches, holy springs (*ayazma*), altars, dervish lodges (*zaviye*, *tekke*), shrines (*türbe*), and tombs (*yatır*) function as emotionally and symbolically charged sites in the collective memory of communities.

These structures, which represent historical, social, and religious continuity, stand out with their symbolic meanings. Yet their transformation has rarely involved destruction or denial; rather, it has often occurred through processes of reinterpretation—eclectic and

syncretic reconstructions that reconcile the present with the sacredness of the past. Each newly arrived religion or belief system typically established its own sacredness atop existing sanctified spaces. Despite changes in religious communities over time, these places often retained their sacral character.

For example, the holy springs known since antiquity as *ayazma*—considered potable and healing—were incorporated during the Christian period into sacred sites associated with saints. These places frequently featured small chapels, altars, or liturgical spaces, and specific rituals were performed with the healing water. In Christian popular belief, such waters served both physical and spiritual purification purposes, being used for baptism, healing, atonement, or the anticipation of miracles (Eyice, 1991: 229). However, with the conquest of the region by Turks and the beginning of Islamization, many of these *ayazmas* were not abandoned; instead, they were reinterpreted within the framework of Islamic popular belief. In this process, the springs were referred to as "healing fountains," "water gifted through the saint's *karāmah*" (miraculous power), or "sacred sources." Around them, tombs and shrines believed to belong to saints (*eren*, *veli*) were erected. In this way, the sacredness associated with water was sustained within a new religious discourse and ritual system under Islam. This transformation not only allowed the local population to maintain a sense of sacredness attached to place but also facilitated the social dissemination of the new faith.

Similarly, graves believed to belong to saints in the Christian era underwent transformations following the advent of Islam. These tombs were later attributed to *eren*, *veli*, or *gazi* figures by Muslim communities and were incorporated into pilgrimage traditions (Işık, 2017: 15–40). Such transformations are frequently observed, particularly in cities that were episcopal centers during the Byzantine period. For instance, a rural sanctuary thought to be associated with a female saint in Antiquity may have been repurposed after conquest as a tomb attributed to a *Horasan eren*, giving rise to local narratives about the figure's miraculous deeds and his role in the region's conquest (Cangul, 2024: 76–90). These narratives are often legitimized through elements of folk belief such as dreams, signs, or miracles (*kerāmet*), and the new sacred identity is built directly upon the older sacred structure.

The modes of transformation undergone by sacred spaces are highly diverse. In this study, the transmission processes of surviving sacred spaces are examined primarily through the framework of Hasluck's typology (2012) and further expanded based on concrete examples identified in the Menderes Basin. In this way, differing transmission forms shaped by historical and cultural contexts are enriched with regional case studies, allowing for a more nuanced and comprehensive evaluation.

2.1. Peaceful Transmission

Peaceful transmission refers to a form of transformation in which sacred spaces are appropriated by a new religious community without physical or symbolic destruction, maintaining their existing sanctity and harmonizing it with the new belief system. In this process, the traces of the previous sacred tradition are not erased; instead, they are incorporated into the new religious framework, thereby expanding the semantic scope of the space while preserving its sacred character. Thus, the space is both preserved and imbued with the sacredness of the new faith. This approach can be regarded as a conciliatory strategy that respects spatial continuity and the perception of sanctity embedded in the collective memory of the local community. Such transformations foster not only cultural continuity but also offer practical advantages. For newly arrived religious groups, repurposing existing structures

provides an economical alternative to building new places of worship, saving both time and resources. Therefore, peaceful transmission emerges as a pragmatic solution and, beyond its cultural compatibility, functions as a means of political stability and social acceptance.

Peaceful transmission also facilitates the integration of the new religious system into the local society. The construction of new meanings upon the preexisting sacred perception prevents the alienation of individuals connected to the old sanctity and simultaneously reinforces the legitimacy of the new faith. Hence, this form of transmission represents not only spatial but also psychological and social continuity. In most cases, architectural elements are preserved during peaceful transmission. Modifications and symbolic interventions mark the presence of the new belief system without erasing the original structure. In Anatolia, particularly during the Seljuk and early Ottoman periods, many churches were converted into mosques through the addition of minarets, and their interiors were rearranged in accordance with Islamic iconography. At the heart of peaceful transmission lies a belief motif that can often be described as "transmigration of the soul" (Işık, 2012: 47) or "spiritual substitution" (Hasluck, 2012: 54). According to this approach, the previous religious identity of a sacred site is not wholly rejected; instead, its spiritual significance is reinterpreted within a new religious framework. For instance, Muslims visiting a Christian sacred site may believe that the saint buried there has been replaced by a Muslim *eren*, or that the same soul has assumed an Islamic form. Conversely, in areas historically dominated by Christian populations, a Muslim *yadır* or *türbe* may be reimagined by local Christians and identified with one of their own saints. Such forms of peaceful transmission are more commonly observed in regions with a multi-religious and multi-layered historical past. However, field research conducted in the Menderes Basin and surrounding areas has not yielded any concrete examples of sacred site transmissions from Islam to Christianity. In contrast, there are several examples of Christian burial structures being reinterpreted within the framework of Islamic folk beliefs and Sufi traditions, thereby transformed into Islamic sacred sites. One such example is the structure known locally as the "Meryem Türbesi" (Shrine of Mary) in the Olukbaşı neighborhood of Bozdoğan district, Aydın province. According to local informants, the shrine is believed to belong to the Virgin Mary. Architectural and symbolic elements supporting this belief include the structure's orientation not facing the *qibla* and the presence of a cross on the tomb beneath the building. According to local oral tradition, the Virgin Mary is believed to have passed away on a mountaintop in the Aegean region alongside her 30 disciples. Based on this narrative, the local population has come to accept the site as belonging to the Virgin Mary (Cangul, 2024: 179). This example from Olukbaşı demonstrates that peaceful transmission is not merely a physical transformation but also a multi-layered spiritual appropriation shaped through narratives, belief motifs, and local memory.

Photo 1. The Shrine of Mary (Meryem Türbesi), Olukbaşı Neighborhood, Kuyucak District, Aydın Province.

2.2. Transfer by Power

Transfer by power refers to the process, especially during conquests and changes of sovereignty throughout history, whereby sacred spaces are seized and redefined by the new dominant powers. In this type of transfer, instead of the physical destruction of the spaces and the sacred meanings they carry, the ruling powers transform and repurpose these places in accordance with their own religious and political ideologies. In this context, transfer by power is considered an important method that has ensured the continuity of sacred spaces throughout history. Transforming the spaces in this way preserves both the economic and architectural value of the existing structures and facilitates the social acceptance of the new faith. However, this process should be understood as a complex set of socio-cultural dynamics, often involving conflicts, resistance, and negotiation.

Most transfers by power occurred in the form of churches being converted into mosques. A significant example of this is the Great Mosque located in the Selçuk district of İzmir, commonly known among locals as the “Church Mosque” or “Fethiye Mosque.” Ibn Battuta provides the following information regarding this: According to reports from the local Greek population, “because it was sacred, visitors used to come here from all directions, but when the city was conquered by Muslims, it was converted into the Friday Mosque known as the Great Mosque” (Ibn Battuta, 424). Today, the mosque is known as Ayasuluk İsabey Mosque.

Photo 2. İzmir, Selçuk, İsa Bey Mosque.

Another concrete example of transfer by power in the context of rural shrine transformation is the Hoca Yusuf Baba Bektashi Lodge located in İzmir Kadifekale. According to local informants, a rural Christian shrine was converted into the tomb of a Muslim saint as a protection measure against Greek looters. Historical records state that in 155 AD, the Bishop of İzmir, St. Polycarp, was targeted for assassination to suppress the spread of Christianity; however, these attempts miraculously failed. It is said that the blood flowing from the bishop's chest extinguished the fire, and he was venerated by the people as a saint who performed miracles. St. Polycarp's bones were buried in Kadifekale, and he was believed to especially protect the region from disasters such as fires and earthquakes. Over time, this saint's grave was appropriated by the Turks, and his name was changed to Yusuf Dede or Yusuf Baba (Ürük-Pınar, 2013: 41).

Photo 3. Yusuf Baba Tomb and Cemetery.

2.3. Transmission Through Reoccupation of Abandoned Sacred Spaces

Transmission through reoccupation of abandoned sacred spaces refers to the process whereby sacred sites that have long been unused or forgotten are rediscovered and re-sacralized by a different religious community at a later period. In this form of transmission, the previous sacred function of the place is not entirely erased; rather, the collective memory and perception of its sacredness are revitalized within the new religious practice over time. Thus, the site continues its historical and cultural continuity, acquiring a new sacred identity and function. Such reoccupations are often marked by spiritual elements like dreams, signs, or sacred experiences, which play a decisive role in the acceptance of the sacredness of the place by new communities. Moreover, the re-sanctification and reuse of abandoned spaces ensure the continuity of regional religious practices and the persistence of social memory.

An important example of this type of transmission can be found in the Akıncılar Çiftliği Tomb in Selçuk district of İzmir province. According to field research, this structure was once a church and was later used as a mosque. Currently abandoned for a long period, this building reflects the multilayered historical nature of sacred sites in the region. A notable detail about the structure is that the stones used in its construction were brought from the ancient city of Ephesus. This indicates that the remains of the ancient period were integrated not only architecturally but also with their symbolic sacred values into subsequent constructions. The fact that the entrance door does not face the qibla suggests that the building was constructed according to earlier architectural traditions, probably Christian, rather than Islamic building principles. Examination of the stonework and architectural features reveals a hybrid character carrying traces of different periods. Particularly, the arrangement of stones on one of the exterior walls shows the use of diverse construction techniques and points to both functional and symbolic transformations of the building over time. In this respect, the Akıncılar Çiftliği Tomb offers a compelling example of how sacred spaces, after being abandoned, are re-sanctified and appropriated by different religious communities. Through its physical remains and folk narratives, the structure reflects the multilayered memory of regional sacredness.

Photo 4. Akıncılar Çiftliği Tomb, Selçuk District, İzmir Province.

Photo 5. Wall of Akıncılar Çiftliği Tomb, Selçuk District, İzmir Province.

2.4. Transmission Through Building a New Sacred Place Next to the Existing One

The transmission of sacredness by constructing a new sacred place adjacent to an existing one is frequently observed in regions conquered by Muslims or where the Christian population has gradually declined. This method not only establishes a spatial proximity but should also be understood as a deliberate strategy aimed at transforming the memory of the old faith. Ahmet Yaşar Ocak explains this situation as follows: “There, by directly confronting the center of the old religion, they used the very means employed by it, gradually weakening its influence and replacing it” (Ocak, 2010: 16-17). As can be understood from this statement, the new sanctuaries built beside the old sacred sites are not coincidental but represent a conscious cultural and religious intervention.

One example of this type of transmission is located in the Bademiye neighborhood of Tire district in İzmir province. In this area, there is a chapel built for Orthodox Christians and a holy spring (ayazma) in front of it. However, as the Christian population began to decline, the chapel fell into disuse, and shortly thereafter, the Ebubekir Ağa Mosque was constructed on the same site. The establishment of the mosque signifies not only the erection of a new physical structure but also a syncretic transformation in which the sanctity of the existing holy spring was incorporated into the Islamic belief system. According to informants, Ebubekir Ağa—believed to have performed miracles in this place—provided water to both Muslims and Christians during a drought period, thereby associating the spring with this new sacred figure. This narrative is summarized as follows: “Ebubekir Ağa was a miraculous man. One day, the villagers suffered from severe drought. Both Christians and Muslims came to this elder’s doorstep. To avoid conflict, the elder caused water to spring forth in the middle. This water is healing. Everyone who comes fills their containers and leaves...” (Cangul, 2024: 418). This story exemplifies a popular memory that continues the sanctity of water through interreligious transition.

Such practices of sacred place transmission are highly significant within the framework of Maurice Halbwachs’ theory of collective memory, particularly concerning the “relationship between social memory and space.” According to Halbwachs, a community sustains its memory

not only in the minds of individuals but also through spaces (2018: 27-60). The holy spring in Bademiye, initially regarded as sacred by Christians and later associated with a Muslim saint by Muslims, demonstrates that this space has been reconstructed by changing social groups through diverse forms of memory. The spring's water here becomes not merely a physical resource but an object of continuity between memories.

Mircea Eliade's concepts of "manifestation of the sacred in space" and "axis mundi" are also instrumental in explaining this transformation. For Eliade, the sacred elevates ordinary space and centers it (Eliade, 1992). The fact that the spring remains sacred for both Christians and Muslims indicates that the original "sacred quality" of the place is not entirely erased over time but rather recoded with new layers of meaning. In this regard, the miracle narrative associated with Ebubekir Ağa is an example of a new sacred story added on top of the old sanctity. These folk narratives should be considered not merely as depictions of a person or event but as collective stories that legitimize the transformation of the space. The miracle narrative functions as a powerful symbolic construct that unites different religious identities and transforms the place into the stage of this unity. Through this narrative, the sanctity of the water is both preserved and adapted to the new belief system, thus ensuring continuity and transformation simultaneously.

Photo 6. Ebubekir Ağa Mosque and Holy Spring in Bademiye Neighborhood, Tire District, İzmir Province.

2.5. Transmission through Objects

In the formation and transformation processes of sacred spaces, the meaning carried by physically sacred objects (such as staffs, stones, garments, soil, etc.) allows the construction of a new realm of sanctity through these objects. In this context, the sanctity attributed to the object is not only symbolic but also serves a directive, indicative, and spatially locational function. In religious literature, such objects are often referred to as relics, talismans, or tokens. Within folk

beliefs, these objects are interpreted as signs of the presence of the sacred and manifestations of its will.

An example of this form of transmission is the legend attributed to Sheikh Kemal in the village of Tamdere, Aydın Province. According to the narrative, when Sheikh Kemal arrived at Tepeköy (its former name), he suffered from thirst and asked a woman for water. The woman delivered the water to Sheikh Kemal through a child. Shortly thereafter, Sheikh Kemal's staff went missing, and following an inner guidance, he found it atop a forested hill in Sarayönü. Seeing the place where the staff was found as a divine sign, Sheikh Kemal established his place there. Over time, this area began to be called Dedeyanı out of respect for him (Tuncer, 1944: 6). In this story, the staff functions both as a physical object and a sacred guide. The lost and subsequently found staff was decisive in Sheikh Kemal's choice of location, and the sacred site was constructed through the meaning associated with this object.

After Sheikh Kemal's death, the arbor where he lived was surrounded by stones by his followers; however, any attempts to cover the grave were thwarted by extraordinary events such as fires. These occurrences were interpreted by the people as "this was Sheikh Kemal's wish," and thus the tomb remained uncovered. Later, a small mosque was built nearby to protect against harsh winter conditions, but due to the belief that Sheikh Kemal "would move there if he wished," the grave site itself was left untouched. This approach clearly reflects the community's ongoing communication with the sacred figure and their respect for his will. Today, the Sheikh Kemal Tomb continues to exist as an expanded form of that mosque. This example is particularly noteworthy in terms of the transmission of sanctity through an object and the recognition, preservation, and ritual continuation of this sanctity by popular belief. The location of the staff defined the sanctity; extraordinary events such as fires delineated its boundaries, and the community preserved Sheikh Kemal's will related to the place through narratives. Thus, the sanctity formed through the object gradually became part of the collective memory both structurally and narratively.

Photo 7. Sheikh Kemal Tomb, Karacasu District, Aydın Province.

2.6. Transmission Through Narrative

The textualization of space enables the construction and guidance of events that occur in that space through a narrative. Since texts do not possess a memory of their own, they have the flexibility to adapt to changing needs over time. Thanks to these characteristics, texts can redefine and direct new situations and spatial uses (Yırtıcı, 2005: 82; cited in Aytaç, 2017: 12). From this perspective, oral narratives play an important role in the continuity and transformation of sacred spaces. In cases where physical structures or sacred objects disappear or their traces are erased, these narratives maintain the presence of sacredness and ensure its reproduction in new spaces. Narratives do not only transmit the past; they also reconstruct, reinforce, and incorporate the meaning of sacred spaces into collective memory. Therefore, transmission through narrative is one of the methods that sustain the continuity of sacred places.

When examined from this viewpoint, narratives serve as bridges connecting the space and the community. The sanctity of the place is enriched by the sacred figures, miracles, rituals, and historical events contained in the narratives. Oral expressions such as “A saint is buried here” or “This stone carries his miraculous touch” transform the place into a living field of sacred memory and play a significant role in the succession of sacred spaces. The transfer of a sacred figure or event from an old sacred place to a new one becomes possible through the reanimation of the narrative in the new location. Thus, the sacred story continues in the new place, and the relationship between sacredness and space becomes flexible and transformable. Narratives in the popular memory keep the identity and meaning of sacred spaces alive, reinforce social belonging, and legitimize religious rituals. Additionally, transmission through narrative can also reflect cultural syncretism and interfaith interaction. Mystical narratives about figures from different religious backgrounds merge with new religious practices, allowing the transformation of the concept of sacred space.

A striking example of sacred space transmission through narrative is the myth related to the ancient city of Nysa in Sultanhisar district, Aydın Province. According to the myth, Dionysus, the god of wine, was born on the mountain where the city is located and was revered by the local people through grape harvest festivals. The name Dionysus is interpreted in Turkish as “The Light God of Nysa Mountain” and was associated with fertility and wine in ancient times. With the spread of Islam in the region, the sacred function of Dionysus related to wine was transferred to the İbirik Dede Shrine. According to informants, Dede makes wine and heals the sick with this wine. This case exemplifies the reinterpretation of ancient pagan figures as Islamic personalities and the continuity of sacred functions through transformation (Cangul, 2024: 93). Thus, the blending of old mythological narratives with local folk beliefs enables sacred spaces to survive with new identities.

Another important example related to the healing function of sacred spaces in the region is the Helvacı Dede Tomb, located near the Amphitheater, a bit ahead of the Asklepion in Bergama. Informants report that Helvacı Dede is a figure who heals patients by preparing and distributing helva (a traditional sweet), and those who eat this helva are said to recover immediately. Moreover, the water found near the tomb is believed to have been brought from the Asklepion and is considered healing (Cangul, 2024: 119). This example demonstrates how the functions associated with the ancient god of health and healing, Asklepios, were reinterpreted through local folk beliefs and sacred space practices.

Fotoğraf 8. İzmir province, Bergama district, Musalla neighborhood, Helvacı Dede Tomb.

The ancient city of Akharaka, located in the Sultanhisar district, was used in antiquity as a thermal treatment center (Strabo, 1917-1932: I.44) and a healing sanctuary. Ethnographic research has identified numerous healing sites, as well as shrines and tombs with healing functions in and around Akharaka. Generally, it can be observed that the roles and attributes of ancient gods were transferred to spiritual figures residing in nearby sacred places (Cangul, 2024: 84). This situation constitutes an important example in terms of the functional continuity of sacred places and religious syncretism (Işık, 2017). In this context, narratives not only transmit the historical background of sacred places from generation to generation but also reinforce the place of these sacred sites in social identity, renew the meaning of the sacred, and sustain the functionality of these spaces by integrating ritual practices. Thus, transmission through narratives is a vibrant and dynamic process that transcends the temporal and spatial boundaries of the sacred, continuously maintaining the existence and significance of sacred places within the collective memory.

2.7. Transmission Through Dreams

In the reconstruction of sacred places within popular memory, dreams function as an important medium of transmission. This type of transmission through dreams often paves the way for the rediscovery and rebuilding of abandoned, physically erased, or forgotten sacred sites. In folk beliefs, dreams are not only personal experiences but are regarded as a means of conveying the sacred, a form of hierophany. In this sense, dreams are considered by the community as an authoritative tool in the re-establishment of sacredness. A concrete example of this is the Hursinli Baba Shrine located in the Karacasu district of Aydın province. According to informants, extraordinary events have long been believed to occur around this shrine; particularly, people with mental health issues reportedly come to this place and are said to be "healed" or "regained sanity." A local resident expresses this belief as follows: "Mad people used to come here and run around the saint. I have heard many stories of people coming here mad and leaving sane, my child..." The narrative that the shrine was revealed in a dream and

subsequently constructed clearly demonstrates the active role of the community in establishing the sacred site. Another informant relates the story as: “Some say this saint was a Christian elder. He appeared in their dreams and said, ‘Build me a tomb, there used to be a church here, that’s what we heard. His name was foreign, they called him Hursinli.’ Then the villagers built this tomb...” (Cangul, 2024: 310).

This example is significant in showing the capacity of dreams to spatially construct sacredness through the agency of the people. The dream is not merely an image retained in an individual's mind; it is a source of motivation that prompts the community to act and directs the process of construction. Today, locals refer to this shrine as the Horasanlı Baba Shrine; thus, this sacred place, re-established through a dream, is integrated into the Islamic belief system, and the formerly ambiguous Christian identity is transformed with a new interpretation. As observed, this process is notable both in terms of the collective memory being reorganized via dreams and the religious identity being rebuilt upon the space. Here, the dream emerges as a powerful instrument that ensures the continuity of sacredness, fills spatial voids, and activates social memory.

Fotoğraf 9. Aydın Province, Karacasu District, Hursinli (Horasanlı) Baba Shrine.

3. Sustainability of Spatial Sanctity; Rituals and Mystical Narratives

Rituals play a crucial and functional role in ensuring the sustainability of sacred spaces. They are not merely a collection of worship or ceremonial behaviors but represent a direct form of relationship with the sacred. According to Eliade (1991: 78), through rituals, humans return to the original moment of creation, the divine act of genesis, experiencing both spiritual and existential renewal. In this sense, ritual is an effort by individuals and societies to re-establish and perpetuate the sacred, symbolizing the transition from chaos to cosmos. From this perspective, even seemingly mundane aspects of daily life such as nutrition, sexuality, taboos, and table manners become ritualized and gain meaning when considered sacred. For an individual excluding the sacred, these actions are merely physiological; however, for one oriented towards the sacred, they are acts of purification, integration, and contact with the

sacred. Thus, ritual plays a central role in constructing sacred space and sustaining its sanctity over time.

Rituals are not only personal pursuits but also a form of social bonding. Durkheim (2005: 45-78) explains the relationship between the sacred and social structures by stating that rituals represent the collective consciousness of society and facilitate individuals' sense of belonging to the community. He argues that totems, taboos, and rituals constitute the building blocks of the bond between the sacred and society. These building blocks ensure the continuity of sacred spaces while strengthening social solidarity.

Field research conducted in the Menderes Basin reveals that ritual practices related to sacred spaces within popular beliefs sustain the sacredness of these places through spatial interaction. These practices generally fall into two categories: object-based rituals and wish/behavior-based rituals (Cangul, 2024: 187-211). Both categories involve direct contact with the sacred, wishing, healing, or spiritual cleansing. These rituals are not exclusive to contemporary folk Islamic practices but are part of a layered belief tradition with historical depth. Indeed, similar practices are observed in ancient pagan and Christian communities as well as in Central Asian shamanistic rituals. Rituals such as tying rags, lighting candles, piling stones, and making vows are performed in both Christian saint cults and shamanic ceremonies to establish contact with the sacred. In this regard, the practices observed in the Menderes Basin can be considered syncretic elements of belief and culture carried into the present day. Among the object-based practices, tying rags, lighting candles, piling stones, and receiving *teberik* (blessed objects) stand out (Cangul, 2024: 187). For example, the ritual of tying rags around the *Çaputlu Dede* and *Çanakçı Baba* shrines in Kuyucak district of Aydın serves as a symbolic expression of the community's faith and expectations. Similar practices can be traced back to springs (*ayazma*) in the ancient period, around the graves of Christian saints, or near sacred mountains and trees revered by shamanic practitioners. Likewise, the practice of *teberik* reception around the *Kıran Dedecik* shrine, where sacred objects are touched or taken, reflects the belief in the material manifestation of the sacred (Cangul, 2024: 200).

Fotoğraf 10. İzmir province, Selçuk district, House of Virgin Mary, wish wall.

Photo 2. 62. Aydın Province, Kuyucak District, Çanakçı Baba Tomb.

Among the practices carried out through wishes and actions are prayers, supplications (niyaz), circumambulation (tavaf), prostration (secde), and animal sacrifice. Prayer is commonly performed at Kuyudağ Dede and Sakköy Dede shrines, while supplication, which involves raising hands in an inner plea, is prevalent at Madran Baba and Telli Dede tombs. The circumambulation observed around shrines such as Sultan Sarı Baba, Eren Dede, and Kadın Dedesi is notable as a local adaptation of the Islamic pilgrimage ritual. Through these acts, individuals symbolically establish closeness to the sacred and create a spiritual ground for their wishes to be granted. All these practices function as ritual tools that ensure the continuity of the sacred both individually and socially, while also carrying layers of historical memory. From the ancient era through Shamanistic beliefs, Christianity, to folk Islam, the fact that rituals performed at sacred sites have been transmitted to the present by changing form but preserving their essence is a remarkable demonstration of syncretic continuity in the region's religious geography.

The sustainability of ritual is not only ensured by physical repetition but also nourished through oral narratives passed down from generation to generation. At this point, mystical narratives come into play. These narratives, which support the function of rituals and concretize the sacred through storytelling, secure the sanctity of places in popular memory. Mystical narratives are belief-based folk tales concerning the miracles, extraordinary powers of sacred figures, and the places associated with them (Önal, 2021, p. 83; Daşdemir, 2024: 97). Encompassing genres such as legends, hagiographies, and memorates, these narratives shape both individual belief and collective memory through oral culture. Similar to myths but more concrete and rooted in local realities, mystical narratives usually revolve around historical figures or places and mostly relate to events closer to the living period of the community. Their main function is to keep the collective memory of sacred places alive and accompany the transformation of the sacred. Extraordinary phenomena included in the narratives — such as foreknowledge of the future, healing, transcending time and space, and influencing nature — appear as common themes across various religious traditions. Field research in the Mendere Basin reveals the role of mystical narratives in cultural continuity. A striking parallel is observed between the narratives associated with Christian saints and those related to Muslim saints in the region. Motifs appearing in Christian hagiographies are also commonly found in accounts of Muslim saints. Although the time and place differ, the plot structure, representations

of sanctity, and the fabric of belief have been transmitted without disruption. These common elements include immunity to fire, walking on water, finding lost objects, foretelling the gender of unborn children, healing powers, and control over natural phenomena.

This similarity indicates that while the sacred transforms, its essence is preserved and intercultural transmission occurs through mystical narratives. Overall, mystical narratives conveyed through oral culture have become a powerful pedagogical tool transmitting the society's values, beliefs, and moral systems to subsequent generations (Önal, 2021: 76). The motifs and symbols contained in the narratives perform explanatory and educational functions, enabling people to sense, experience, and reproduce the sacred within their worldview (Güngör, 1982: 106; Wellek et al., 1983: 252–253). Therefore, the sustainability of sacred places is realized through the continuity of rituals and narratives. Rituals reconstruct sacred time and space, while mystical narratives provide meaning and origin to these rituals. Thanks to this dual structure, the sacred maintains its spatial continuity, persists within social memory, and remains the foundation of religious life despite changing cultural contexts.

CONCLUSION

The Menderes Basin stands out as a unique religious geography where multiple faiths and religious systems have historically intertwined, allowing a tangible observation of the relationship between the sacred and space. Within this historical continuity extending from ancient beliefs to Christianity and Islam, the relationship between the sacred and space is examined not only from a religious perspective but also within sociological, cultural, and phenomenological frameworks. Accordingly, this study has evaluated the transformation and continuity of sacred spaces around the concept of “syncretism,” revealing how religious identities and rituals are reinterpreted through spatial contexts. The analysis of 228 sacred sites (temples, churches, rural sanctuaries, holy springs, shrines, tombs) in the region has been considered concrete examples of religious syncretism. The transformation of a space belonging to one faith into a religious site of another system through a process of religious accommodation demonstrates that these structures are re-sanctified not only physically but also symbolically, mythologically, and functionally.

In the study, these transformations are classified under seven main headings. Three of these are based on Hasluck's classification: “Peaceful Transfer,” “Power-Based Transfer,” and “Resettlement to an Abandoned Place.” The other four—“Transfer Through Building a New Sacred Space Adjacent to the Old,” “Transfer Through Objects,” “Transfer Through Narratives,” and “Transfer Through Dreams”—are original categories proposed in this work based on field research findings in the Menderes Basin. Within these categories, each mode of transmission is illustrated with local examples; the place of sacred space transformations in religious continuity, cultural transmission, and collective memory is analyzed and conceptualized through the lens of folk beliefs. A particularly noteworthy point is that from the perspective of “sacred space,” this transformation process is not merely a historical transition but a meaning map constructed with popular memory and cultural codes. The cycle of sacred space folklore, oral narratives, and rituals nourishes the cultural codes of society through esoteric tales, producing a symbolic language that ensures the continuity of belief. In this framework, two main elements emerge as crucial: sacred space memory and popular memory. The interaction between these two memory planes has made it possible to understand the integrative, unifying, and complementary belief structure of the Menderes Basin.

The theoretical framework employed in the study is built upon Rudolf Otto's focus on the transcendent nature of the sacred, Mircea Eliade's sacred–profane dichotomy, Durkheim's emphasis on the social construction of the sacred, and the collective and cultural memory theories advanced by Halbwachs, Jan Assmann, and Pierre Nora. This theoretical structure demonstrates that religious transformations are not only historical and theological but deeply intertwined with social memory and cultural transmission. Consequently, the sacred sites in the Menderes Basin are spaces where different belief systems come together not through conflict but through interaction and overlap, sustaining the sacred in a multilayered and time-extended manner. This study reveals how spatial sanctity is reproduced in syncretic forms and maintained through social memory, thereby making a theoretical and methodological contribution to social sciences literature in terms of religious pluralism, cultural continuity, and the religion–space relationship. It clearly shows that the domain where resistance to all change is most intense is the phenomenon of “sacred space” within the context of religion and belief.

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